

Swinostics

Swine diseases field diagnostics toolbox

Newsletter N° 2 - October 2018

The project is funded by Horizon 2020, the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation for 2014-2020 under grant agreement No 771649.

SUSTAINABLE FOOD SECURITY – RESILIENT AND RESOURCE-EFFICIENT VALUE CHAINS
Call identifier: H2020-SFS-2016-2017

Swinostics news

To develop the Swinostics device, during this period the consortium has been working on the development of the different modules. **Fig.1** presents the overall approach and configuration.

Fig.1 Swinostics conceptual design

The Swinostics team is aiming at the development of a portable device that will require 20 minutes for the simultaneous analysis of 5 samples, to detect 6 different swine emerging and endemic viruses (**Fig. 2**). Commercial monoclonal antibodies were selected and will be characterized for their binding capability.

Targeted Virus	SWINOSTICS Samples
✓ African Swine Fever (ASF)	Oral fluid in live animals, blood serum from postmortem animals
✓ Porcine Reproductive and respiratory Syndrome (PRRS)	Oral fluid and blood serum
✓ Swine Influenza A (SIV)	Oral fluid and nasal swabs
✓ Porcine Parvovirus (PPV)	Oral fluid and faeces
✓ Porcine Circovirus (PCV2)	Oral fluid
✓ Classical Swine Fever (CSF)	Oral fluid in live animals, blood serum from postmortem animals

Fig.2 Swine viruses selected in the project and their matrix

The **Swinostics 6M** meeting was hosted on the 19th-20th April 2018 in Paestum, Italy and it was organised by CNR. All partner organizations attended the event. During the two-days meeting the consortium discussed the main technical and open issues.

Fig.3 M6 meeting in Paestum

The main activities planned in the next months are:

- Identification, purification and characterization of the single antibodies molecules
- Design of the optical module of the Swinostics device
- Design and development of the PIC configuration and microfluidic units
- Dissemination and communication activities

The **Swinostics 12M** meeting was hosted on the 23rd-24th October 2018 in Warsaw, Poland and it was organised by PiWet.

Fig.4 M12 meeting in Warsaw

All partner organizations attended the event and during the meeting the consortium discussed the status of development of the main components of the device . The main deliverables in the next six months were discussed (**Figure 5**).

Fig.5 Swinostics Deliverables Roadmap

- ✓ A video interview to Dr. Amadeu Griol (UPV) on the Swinostics project was published on the YouTube Channel of Universidad Politécnica de Valencia (**Fig 6**)

Fig 6. UPV YouTube interview

- ✓ The main social media accounts for the Swinostics project were created (**Fig.7**)

Website: www.swinostics.eu
Facebook: www.facebook.com/swinostics/
LinkedIn: www.linkedin.com/company/18392774
Twitter: www.twitter.com/swinostics

Fig 7. Swinostics social media

Next events:

- ✓ UVMB will participate in the PRRS Symposium (www.vet.k-state.edu/na-prrs), Chicago, USA from 1st-2^{sd} December 2018 (**Fig. 8**), presenting a poster on Swinostics.
- ✓ Two publications on the Swinostics project will be submitted on international journals

Fig 8. PRRS Symposium website

Swinostics Consortium

